

The Importance of Sustainability in Total Quality Management Practices in Corporate Organization in Ghana

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Abstract

Objective: This study investigated on the importance of sustainability in total quality management practices in corporate organizations in Ghana.

Methods: A systematic review of empirical and conceptual work across several disciplines was conducted. The literature study identified and examined relevant material on TQM, sustainability management, environmental sustainability, employee performance, operational performance, and organizational outcomes. Research from manufacturing, education, small and medium businesses as well as other organizational contexts were included to have a comprehensive understanding of the study.

Results: The findings of this research suggest that TQM has positive influence on staff performance, customer satisfaction, knowledge management, operational efficiency and management effectiveness. The paper also illustrates that TQM promotes sustainability efforts via continuous improvement, organizational learning and stakeholder interaction and innovation. Strategies of environmental sustainability and green innovation have been identified as important ways for organizations to mitigate environmental impacts and improve competitiveness and long-term performance. The research on the direct effect of TQM on financial performance is still equivocal, although most studies indicate favorable outcomes on organizational sustainability and overall performance.

Conclusion: TQM is a strategic management approach that leads to sustainable organizational performance. Integrating TQM concepts with environmental sustainability and green innovation methodologies may be a driver of organizational resilience, enhance operational performance and lead to the production of long-term economic, social and environmental value.

Keywords: Total, Quality, Management, Sustainability, Organization, Ghana.

Introduction

The business industry has increased the demand for businesses to sustain their operations especially with holistic management techniques rapidly. Total Quality Management is based on the idea that performance may be achieved in a quality-oriented environment where all members of the firm work together to improve processes continuously for the long-term sustainability (1). Total quality management is a systematic way to plan, understand and organize activities that are different for every person at every phase (2).

Six of the seventeen Sustainable Development Goals are directly focused on promoting environmental sustainability. The six Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs 6, 7, 11, 12, 13 and 14) focus on clean water and sanitation, affordable and clean energy, sustainable cities and communities, responsible consumption and production, climate action and conservation of marine life. But in addition to human efforts, the way companies function is key to achieving these goals. All industries have seen companies acknowledge the need to embrace ecologically

friendly practices (3,4). The commencement of sustainability takes place in the area of human resource management in organizations (3,5).

With the growth of manufacturing in different economies, the environment is severely harmed (6,7). Manufacturing activities have made environmental concerns such as global warming, pollution, climate change and land degradation widespread and therefore threatening environmental safety (8,9). Greenhouse gas emissions in the world economies are mostly caused by industrial activities, which contribute around 60% of total emissions and affect environmental safety, operational efficiency and human health (10). According to the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (11), millions of lives are lost each year in these nations owing to worsening environmental problems.

Green human resource management (green HRM) practices have been developed as a strategic approach to integrate environmental sustainability into the core human resource management (HRM) functions of organizations, to create a sustainable workplace and promote the internalization of environmental sustainability among employees (12,13,14). Green HRM is defined as the employer's ways of encouraging employees to behave in an ecologically sustainable way in the workplace via the implementation of various techniques to achieve environmental sustainability (15,16). Green HRM involves the introduction of environmental consciousness into corporate human resource management activities such as job analysis, recruitment and selection, orientation and training, performance appraisal, incentives and pay, and health and safety at work (16).

The study investigates the role of sustainability in enterprises via comprehensive principles of quality management in Ghana. This will improve knowledge of the implementation of sustainable concepts, while guaranteeing a safe working environment for staff.

Total Quality Management Theory

As the global economy grows, quality is becoming more necessary for companies to succeed. Total Quality Management (TQM) is a strategy for improving customer satisfaction and organizational performance through the delivery of quality goods and services by involving and collaborating with all stakeholders and applying quality management methodologies and tools (17). In the backdrop of the increased global economic development, companies are working towards achieving and sustaining high levels of performance and effectiveness in the workplace. Companies are facing a turbulent global economic market that puts pressure on quality, customer satisfaction, productivity, economic uncertainty, organizational culture, and technological innovation (18).

Quality is important to the economic success of manufacturing enterprises (19). The concept of Total Quality Management (TQM) has evolved in the context of strong global competition. The ideas, methods, tools and techniques of Total Quality Management (TQM) have been the focus of much attention by firms operating in the worldwide market and global competitiveness. Porter and Tanner (20) state that "Total quality management is a management approach that is focused on improving a business' effectiveness, competitiveness and responsiveness to the needs of consumers and other stakeholders to achieve long term growth in organizational performance.

Corporate Sustainability Theory

Corporate sustainability is the pursuit of environmental, social and economic goals in order to achieve sustainable prosperity (21,22). This implies that business sustainability is sustainable development, which is "meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" with social, economic, and environmental possibilities (23). This is innovation in the organizational business model, which may double

the chance of returns on other kinds of capital (e.g. social, environmental) instead of simply on economic capital (21).

Sustainable development is based on the triple bottom line paradigm (24), which implies the simultaneous assessment of three different types or forms of capital: economic, social and environmental (25), which are interrelated and influence each other in numerous ways. The economic aspect ensures constant liquidity and generates profits for the owners of the organization (26) and it is focused on the economic value that permits the survival of the organization by supporting future generations (25). The environmental dimension is about not doing things that degrade ecosystem services and committing to the best use of natural resources and reduction of emissions (26). The social dimension is increasing the value of the communities in which the organisation operates by 'increasing the human capital of individual partners and boosting the social capital of those communities' (26). This involves addressing issues of employee relations, fair remuneration and community involvement (25), as well as gaining the understanding and agreement of the stakeholders in terms of the organization's motives and ideals (26).

Sustainable development should be included in the day to day total quality management of organizations for long-term profitability and sustainability. However, the dynamic environment is still affecting the underlying conditions, making it difficult to achieve sustainable development (27). The organizations need to be resilient and adapt to the context to restructure their operations for equity, environmental sustainability and economic prosperity.

Sustainability Measurement

The sustainability assessment at the organizational level consists of two techniques, namely 1. 2. Criteria-based approaches Model-based approaches provide the most suitable alternative (28). Sustainability evaluation at the company level may also be considered in the context of the performance-measurement driven model and the maturing-measurement driven approach (29). Because of the limitations of the existing metrics of OS, the present authors have developed composite indices to measure OS (30). The measurement models are the Genuine Progress Indicator, the Minnesota Progress Indicator and the Triple Bottom Line.

The Genuine Progress Indicator (GPI) is a statistic that attempts to evaluate the economic well-being of a country by including environmental and social factors that are ignored by traditional GDP assessments. It comprises 25 variables relating to economic, environmental and social concerns. The aim is to provide a broader picture of a country's progress by including the positive and negative consequences of economic activity (31). The Minnesota Progress Indicator is a holistic tool to measure progress towards a strong and sustainable economy. It includes 42 economic, environmental and community indicators that give a more accurate and comprehensive picture of the state's progress. The indicator aims to ensure that economic progress does not come at the expense of communities or the environment but includes comprehensive economic activity (32,33).

The notion of the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) was submitted to the United Nations General Assembly in 2005. This idea was later called the 'triple bottom line' and systematised by Elkington as an accounting system to measure the performance of corporate America (34). This approach has extended traditional measures of financial success such as profit, return on investment and shareholder value to incorporate a broader perspective that considers the social and environmental effects of performance. The triple bottom line is an increasingly common basic framework for establishing sustainability standards, certifications and principles across a range of industries (35,36). The TBL framework is extensively utilized by social businesses, including for-profit and non-profit organizations, and government agencies at the federal, state and local levels to meet sustainability goals (37,38).

Deborah mentioned economic problems such as fair allocation of resources and technology transfer challenges such as technology spillover (39). Social challenges include issues such as human rights violations, labour rights and increased health and safety regulations. Environmental problems include climate change, waste management, recycling and finding ways to generate energy from different sorts of wastes such solid, electronic and hazardous wastes. Deborah described certain environmental challenges as 'wicked problems', and defined climate change as the 'super wicked problem' for leaders to confront (39). Many managers feel that not enough is being done to improve the productivity of human capital for sustainability in view of complex concerns described above (40,41,42). Therefore, it has been pointed out that other techniques should be devised to improve financial performance while minimizing bad impacts on a firm's socio-environmental elements (43).

One of the biggest drawbacks of Elkington's TBL model, despite its wide usage, is the lack of a measurement for each of the three core pillars of development, namely, environment, society and economics. This disadvantage has decreased the usefulness of the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) in assessing performance in terms of sustainability (44). However, others have seen the lack of universally accepted standards for the assessment of TBL performance as a positive attribute. As argued by Slaper and Hall, this flexibility is a strength because it enables users to adapt the general framework to different entities (business or non-profit), different projects or policies (infrastructure investments or educational programs), or different geographic boundaries (a city, region, or country) (44).

Brundtland's efforts to define sustainability prompted Robert to construct the structure of the natural step (45,46). This framework sets forth the conditions that need to be fulfilled for the sustainability of human activity on Earth. It also identifies four key needs that a society should pay attention to in its commitment to sustainable development. This framework also prohibited the extraction of material from the earth, the stop of all human-made substance production and the cessation of all actions that disturb the natural environment.

The framework offers a method, 'back-casting from principles' to steer societies to sustainability. Economic and industrial institutions have failed to prevent environmentally damaging actions. Sustainability requires the inclusion of 'systems thinking' and 'back-casting from sustainability principles' to use different tools and techniques in the planning and re-engineering of management domains such as organizational strategies, processes and new product development.

Impact assessment for sustainability The Commission of the European Communities defined impact assessment as a concept that 'identifies the probable positive and negative effects of proposed policy actions, facilitating informed political decisions regarding the proposals and recognizing trade-offs in achieving conflicting objectives' (47). Based on impact assessment the European Union developed rules globally and improved them via several revisions (47,48) including the ones performed by the Secretariat General EU.

Financial performance of firm sustainability strategies is commonly measured by the Dow Jones Sustainability Indices (DJSI) (49). The DJSI is mainly intended to track the financial performance of best-in-class sustainability companies. S & P Dow Jones Indices suggest that all firms should start sustainability now in order to be competitive in the future (49).

The arrival of the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has increased the gap in sustainability assessment at the macro and micro levels. The need for more realistic sustainability measures is therefore critical (50). To address this gap, scholars have suggested a nexus method (51). Currently there are numerous well-known indicators to measure the performance of Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs) at the national level notably Sustainable Development and The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Distance measure (52,53). Eurostat report-based progress indicators (54). Chang et al. confirmed that Corporate Sustainability (CS) is an extension of Corporate Social

Responsibility (CSR) (55). There are scholars who say that OS and CS are similar concepts, with OS being a more modern term (56).

Computer Science is a difficult subject, which has been developed step by step since the 1980s and it has been accepted. Analysis of the literature found that this concept has several interpretations, frequently lacks clarity, refers to different behaviours, and still allows for future expansion (57,58). This model argues that the early stages of CS are often characterized by some opposition to its implementation. In this paradigm, Dunphy et al. pointed out that sustainable goals and organizational activities interventions and kinds of effective leadership differ at the different levels of CS (59).

Here are some usual definitions of computer science. The firm is a profit-making corporation in a constant state of development. This entity is a system of resources and networks of relationships with stakeholders. Employees of the firm are tasked with representing the organization, managing its resources, and engaging its stakeholders to ensure legal compliance, uphold its 'license-to-operate', improve competitive advantage, and contribute to the development of more sustainable societies by addressing the economic, environmental, social and temporal axes in an integrated manner. This ability is the firm's ability to meet current financial demands without impairing the firm's or other entities' ability to meet future needs (60,61). Therefore, time is essential to the idea of sustainability.

Responding to the needs of a company's direct and indirect stakeholders such as shareholders, workers, consumers, advocacy groups and communities, while being able to meet future needs (62). Corporate initiatives that actively seek to achieve sustainability equilibria, including the economic, environmental and social aspects of the present, as well as their interconnections over time, taking into account the company's systems (Operations and Production, Management and Strategy, Organizational Systems, Procurement and Marketing, and Assessment and Communication) and its stakeholders (63).

The company's initiatives are voluntary in nature and demonstrate the integration of social and environmental concerns into the company's activities and interactions with its stakeholders (64). A genuinely sustainable firm embeds sustainability in its corporate strategy and communicates its sustainability aim internally and internationally. It provides long-term benefit in the financial, social, environmental and ethical aspects (65,66). company sustainability is an integrated company approach and strategy that takes into account the long term social and environmental effects of any profit-seeking activities of a firm touching consumers, employees, owners, or shareholders (67).

A McKinsey poll of 1,946 executives across industries and countries found that most business leaders still don't know what sustainability means (68). In this survey, 55% of the respondents linked sustainability to the environment, 48% saw it as a governance problem connected to regulatory compliance, ethical behaviors and adherence to industrial standards, while 41% of the executives considered sustainability as a social concern.

To stimulate interest and investment in sustainability for both firms and investors, a business plan is needed that generates long-term shareholder value by taking advantage of the possibilities and reducing the risks of economic, environmental and social development. The stronger this circle of benefit grows, the beneficial influence it will have on the society and economy of rich and poor countries alike (69).

The literature on Corporate Sustainability (CS) shows that its development started from corporate governance (70,71), and then expanded to ecological economics (72), ethical and responsible corporate conduct (73), CSR investment for organizational profitability(74), sustainability leadership in the context of resource conservation [7], human resource development investment for organizational sustainability, challenges in eco-leadership, and the interaction between social responsibility and stakeholders in organizational decision-making (75,76).

In summary, on the one hand, the literature indicates that sustainability is defined as the corporate actions that use the financial resources of a firm in a way that benefits society and the natural environment through philanthropy (78), and on the other hand, sustainability is related to sustainability values embedded as fundamental principles that continuously support the Triple Bottom Line (78).

The growing academic interest and the growing public demand for sustainable organizations have raised complex economic challenges for the transition of traditional organizations into sustainable organizations (79). Dunphy et al. and Sari have identified internal and external elements as accelerators for the shift of enterprises to sustainability (57,28).

External pressures include government agencies, communities, consumers, market expectations, competitive enterprises, industry associations, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). Internal pressures may originate from executives and other change agents in the organization, such as employees, stockholders and investment companies, who are aware of the benefits of, and push for, OS (80). Internal operations like marketing, human resources and manufacturing typically try to incorporate sustainability into their organizational procedures.

Avery (81) suggested four criteria for evaluating the sustainability of an organization: 1) An operation is unsustainable if it leads to undesirable consequences for its contractual partners (unhappy workers, owners, and consumers).

A corporation that produces positive benefits for the voluntary stakeholders (e.g. content workers, owners, and customers) but negative consequences for non-contracting parties (e.g. depleting non-renewable resources or a farmer exceeding his legal water rights) is only sustainable.

a. If no one is accountable for the negative consequences of the organization

b. ... until the total negative impact of similar companies, like the fishing industry, where fish are removed faster than they can breed, finally destroys the entire industry.

A business strategy that produces positive outcomes for the contractual parties (e.g., content workers, owners, and consumers) but negative consequences for major non-contracting groups (e.g., pollution, poverty, and social alienation) is not sustainable and should not be continued.

A sustainable organization or business model has positive consequences for contracting and non-contracting stakeholders alike. Dunphy et al. describe embedding sustainability inside firms as a progressive change process that requires different strategies and leadership capabilities relevant to each stage (57).

More and more scholars and practitioners see sustainability as a major organizational

A strategy that may provide competitive advantage to companies. At the same time, the increased complexity in the business world and the uncertainties that CS is facing have become a major problem for the organizations (82,83).

The survival of firms amid turbulence consists on the creation of an operating system as a competitive advantage (84). It has been suggested that to maximize the efficacy of OS, the firm's strategy should be realigned and revamped to identify demands for activities that are less harmful to the environment and society (83).

Sustainability: Investment Approach

Opportunity Researchers wrote that CEOs see sustainability as an investment opportunity with expected results (85). In addition, researchers have asserted that firms may include stakeholders in CSR initiatives to develop loyalty and increase financial performance (86,87). Researchers have found contradictory results for the association between a firm's sustainability investments and financial success in different contexts (88,89). Other non-financial benefits of sustainability initiatives include skilled workforce, better marketing opportunities via green competitiveness, brand repositioning, better brand image and social and ecological

certifications. Some studies have shown the ability of CS to improve organizational performance (90).

Methods

In this research, we aim to analyze and importantly, identify the academic and corporate practices within the sustainability initiative. This study used a systematic literature review. A systematic literature review “locates existing studies, selects and evaluates contributions, analyses and synthesizes data, and reports the evidence in such a way that allows reasonably clear conclusions to be reached about what is and is not known” (91).

A systematic review was carried out with the aid of online research journal websites as well as other in-context articles. While conducting this study, the keywords in the search query were directed toward the the need for sustainability in total quality management practices. Areas noted in relation to this study were the implementation of sustainability in their operation practices. Therefore, there was a linkage of papers pointing out the integration of sustainable practices in organizations day to day operations. In addition, the researcher emphasizes that action research is extremely valuable in gaining insights into managerial sense-making, sense-giving, and the impact on decision-making in the midst of change interventions.

Results

Implementation of Total Quality Management (TQM) was implemented to employees in Sidoarjo, East Java, showing a correlation between TQM and knowledge management on the performance of employees in the animal feed manufacturing sector (92) and on the operational performance of other enterprises (93). One of the focus components in the application of the TQM model is customer satisfaction that has a positive relationship (94,95) with the effect of work quality (96). The implementation of Total Quality Management has effectively changed Muhammadiyah Prambanan Vocational School into an institution with a spirit of continuous quality improvement (97).

From the Islamic perspective, Total Quality Management may improve the organizational performance and the individual awareness inside the organization (98). The relationship between HRM factors and Total Quality Management (TQM) is explained by the positive relationship between TQM, job motivation and employee performance (99,100). Furthermore, management performance is linked to the TQM model (101,102) and financial success (103). Performance measuring systems and incentive systems modulate the effect of TQM on management performance in firms (104). albeit the remuneration system also has a considerable effect on employee performance, albeit not as large as Total Quality Management (TQM) (105). Therefore, along with human performance, organizational performance is one of the variables influenced by TQM (106). Wesly et al. research shows that Total Quality Management influences Sustainability Management as a variable (107).

The research by Chaerunisak and Aji (108) found that Total Quality Management (TQM) did not influence company profitability, but it did affect management performance in case studies of micro, small, and medium businesses (MSMEs). Meanwhile, the research of Khoviani and Izzaty (109) and Lestari and Sutrisna (110) found a positive effect of TQM on operational performance in other MSMEs. Sustainability and organizational performance are two important concerns to be researched in the current days. A study was conducted to determine the main learning components and measure learning performance thus enabling effective sustainability. The results are summarized in a sustainability learning performance framework (111). The link between corporate financial performance and corporate social performance has been widely investigated, with mixed findings (112). Another study contributes to the detailed exploration of port operational sustainability, particularly the evaluation of the results of its

implementation (113). There is increasing interest among operations management practitioners in sustainability and its link with performance (114). Hristov and Chirico (115) explored significant performance indicators that affect the success of the firm and proposed a new approach for incorporating sustainability issues into business plans.

Total Quality Management sees quality as a long term strategic strategy for businesses to offer products and services that fulfill explicit and implicit expectations of internal and external stakeholders. The key to continuity, strength and sustained performance resides in the issue of measurement. Total Quality Management is a strategic initiative that seeks to improve the total quality of goods by identifying, improving and eliminating flaws in the operational processes of organizations (116). Sustainability is described as the continuous maintenance of systems based on economic, environmental and social factors (117). Allur et al. (118) have done a conceptual and empirical study of the literature on the link between sustainability and Quality Management from many viewpoints, frameworks and techniques. Zairi (119) has proposed a framework called as Total Quality Management Capability and Sustainable Performance Model (TQM-MSPM). The TQM Capability and Sustainable Performance Model assumes the need for an organizational structure that encourages collaboration, learning and innovation to implement process management ideas.

During an era of resource restrictions and ecological challenges, over-dependence on nonrenewable resources may become unsustainable. The strategy decisions of the majority of the enterprises encounter issues such as pollution, poor waste management, high energy consumption, and climate change in the industrial sector (120). Many industrial enterprises are quickly adopting sustainable practices of circular economy, which allow the reduction, reuse, recycling and redesign of goods and services, thus reducing the dependence on virgin resources and finding alternative uses of waste (121). Environmental sustainability refers to all the practices undertaken by an organization to meet the demand for resources and services by the current and future generations while conserving the health of the environment that provides those resources (122). Environmental sustainability is the responsible interaction of industrial firms with the environment, aiming to reduce or avoid the depletion or degradation of natural resources, therefore conserving their quality over time.

Green innovation is directly related to the construct of environmental sustainability. Green innovation, also known as eco-innovation or environmental innovation, involves changing organizational processes to avoid or reduce environmental damage (123). Green innovation is the commercial reaction to environmental problems caused by bad practices, which are not sustainable. Many industrial businesses are using the circular business model to build supply chains that retrieve or recycle resources utilized in the development of new items (124). The earlier studies reveal that the green innovation techniques are preferred more owing to the benefits to the firms, stakeholders, and the environment (125).

Many studies have identified the environmental sustainability practices of an organization as a key precursor for green innovation behavior (126,127) leading to the commercial and economic benefits for the firm (128). There are many theories, strategies and performance indicators proposed to help organizations survive, but there are still large gaps in the understanding of how to identify sustainable routes, assess sustainable alternatives and implement sustainability transitions (129). The organization's collective vision of sustainability is realized by the involvement of stakeholders in the formulation of sustainable business decisions.

Hargett and Williams (130) recommended that cultural conflicts or discrepancies can be reduced by establishing a single communication platform, developing best practices for different national cultures, using a systematic method for incorporating the TBL into the organization's internal and external operations, increasing the understanding of CSR among employees, encouraging diversity in the organization, especially at the headquarters, and developing a sponsorship strategy highlighting the key projects the company wants to support

and finance, as well as the rationale behind these sponsorship decisions. Furthermore, other ideas suggested to solve these difficulties in achieving operational sustainability include fostering systems thinking, nexus thinking and integrating Industry 4.0. The transition to OS will be facilitated by the collaboration of stakeholders taking into consideration the organizational dynamics, that is, the alignment of the organizational capability with the external environment (129).

Conclusion

The study findings reveal that Total Quality management (TQM) is an important organizational strategy that has a positive influence on employees' performance, operational efficiency, managerial efficacy, knowledge management, customer satisfaction, and organizational sustainability. The results from many sectors such as manufacturing, education, and small to medium companies show that Total Quality Management promotes continuous improvement, enhances organizational learning, and improves competitive advantage. Although some studies have shown mixed findings on the direct impact of TQM on financial profitability, most studies have confirmed its significant contribution to managerial and operational performance.

Environmental concerns, resource constraints and rising stakeholder expectations mean sustainability is now a key business aim. The integration of sustainability principles with Total Quality Management provides companies with a complete framework to achieve sustainable economic, environmental and social performance. Environmental sustainability practices and green innovation initiatives have become important ways for organizations to enhance sustainable performance and minimize their environmental footprint. The research reviewed indicates that organizations that integrate quality management systems with sustainability-oriented activities are more likely to achieve long-term resilience, operational excellence, and stakeholder value creation.

Theoretical Implications

This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge via explaining the relationship between Total Quality Management, sustainability and organizational performance. It draws upon knowledge from different industries and contexts to demonstrate that TQM is a core competence that underlies both organizational effectiveness and sustainable development objectives.

The results also further supports the theoretical link between TQM Capability and Sustainable Performance Model (TQM-SPM) and environmental sustainability and green innovation. It highlights the way quality management concepts foster organizational learning, continuous improvement, stakeholder engagement and inventive abilities that are vital for sustainable transitions. This study adds to the literature on sustainability management by showing that Total Quality Management (TQM) can be a strategic enabler of environmental sustainability and green innovation thereby closing the gap between two distinct research streams in quality management and sustainable business.

Practical Implications

The findings have a number of practical consequences for managers, politicians and organizational leaders. Total Quality Management should be seen as a strategic endeavor for the long term rather than an operational tool by organizations. Engaged workforce, constant improvement, streamlining processes and putting the customer first may significantly boost corporate success.

Secondly, managers aim to embed sustainability objectives into existing quality management systems to provide synergistic benefits. Firms may improve resource efficiency, minimize

waste, reduce environmental impacts, and build stakeholder trust by combining TQM standards with environmental sustainability goals.

Invest in green innovation skills, such as sustainable product development, eco-friendly procedures, circular economy strategies and resource recovery systems. These initiatives contribute to environmental protection as well as to competitive advantages and new economic opportunities.

Leaders of organizations must foster a culture of collaboration, learning and innovation and include stakeholders in sustainability decision-making processes. Strong leadership commitment, effective communication system, performance evaluation systems and employee awareness creation are needed for successful implementation of Total Quality Management and continued organizational performance in a more complex business environment.

Consent

It is not applicable.

Ethical Approval

It is not applicable.

Competing Interests

Author has declared that no competing interests exist.

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Data availability

This manuscript has no associate data.

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